

THE PROCEDURE FOR USING PSYCHODIAGNOSTIC METHODS IN THE MILITARY SPHERE

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Annotation: *this article analyzes the historical formation of military psychology and the tasks and structure of the science of psychodiagnostics, the development of which as a branch of modern science is of particular importance, as well as the main areas of psychodiagnostics in the military sphere as an independent science and its problems in perspective, based on several psychological sources not included in scientific consumption.*

Key words: *military community, psyche, moral and psychological training, strengthening the human psyche, scientific psychological knowledge, military psychology, psychology of the Military Personnel, Psychology of Group and interpersonal relations in the army, psychology of military activity during peace, psychology of military discipline, psychology of combat and war.*

In the world, regular reforms are being carried out by the states to improve the intellectual, moral, professional and physical training of military personnel. The supreme goal of the States is to ensure the peaceful and prosperous survival of their people. It is considered important that each state has a strong army in the international arena. Psychodiagnostics is one of the areas of Psychological Science and includes the following stages:

1. Study of the referral of the recipient to a psychologist. Since the appeal to diagnostics is in a simple, vital colloquial language, it is necessary to turn it into a scientific psychological manifestation, that is, to outline a psychological problem on the basis of the practical requirement made. Deep understanding of the problem as an observer from the outside.

2. To solve the problem, collect primary information on the incoming demand: about the successful performance of family members, activities (training or Labor); about their relationship with those nearby; medical conclusion; collection of Anamnesis.

3. The selection of diagnostic methods for advancing the hypothesis and its verification based on the information collected.

4. Conducting a diagnostic examination, processing and analyzing the results.

5. Drawing basic conclusions based on the diagnostic data obtained.

6. Psychological assistance, identification of types of influence, that is, the development of practical recommendations, the definition of the main orientation for consultation work.

Preparation of testing conditions the place of study should be free from various external interference, while meeting sanitary and hygienic rules. A work situation that does not force must be ensured. The technical support of the study should correspond to the issues to be addressed. It is necessary to select the verifiers to be qualitatively identical. - the researcher influences the course of the study, the conduct of all its stages; - before the start of the instruction or research, the preparatory stage is drawn up. it should be clear, concise and

unambiguous; - the results of the study should be recorded in statements, it should be both full and targeted at the same time; - the data from the study should be qualitatively and quantitatively analyzed-synthesized, that is, processed. The most important task for a psychodiagnost is to make the right psychological diagnosis as well as determine the work of psychocorrection. The types of psychological assistance are very diverse: psychotherapy (its purpose is the psychological health of a person), individual counseling, as well as correction-group work on development, which is used to help individuals with various psychological difficulties. L.S. In the practice of psychological research on vigotsky, 3 stages of psychological diagnosis are distinguished: symptomatic diagnosis is also called empirical diagnosis. In this case, the diagnosis is limited to the emphasis on certain signs or characteristics, on the basis of which practical conclusions are drawn. L.S. Vigotsky notes that such a diagnosis is not considered scientific, since the identification of signs does not automatically lead to a direct diagnosis. The second stage in the development of psychological diagnosis is etiological diagnosis, taking into account not only the presence of certain characteristics and signs of the individual, but also the causes that cause the problem. The most ynqori stage is the typological stage. In this case, the OMI and ahaniyati in the personality structure of the information gained are determined. For example, 1 .Symptomatic diagnosis: "attention deficit syndrome and hyperactivity". 2. Etiological diagnosis: "attention deficit syndrome and hyperactivity caused by genetic as well as socio-psychological factors (prenatal, postnatal development - preterm birth of a child; exposure to toxic, toxic substances; impaired MNT I; hypoxia and anoxia, excessive or rash of y'ani weight; emotional complexities between parents; severity of material conditioning; psychic deprivation; nonconditioning, etc.)". Relying on the above considerations, it can be said that when organizing psychodiagnostic work, a psychologist must follow a number of requirements:

First of all, a psychologist should know and be able to apply the basics of differential psychometry and methods of analysis of the psychological literature, practical application of the general theoretical and methodological principle.

Secondly, it is necessary to create an information data bank and a Bank of test tools.

Thirdly, the decision that the psychologist conducting psychodiagnostic examinations makes on the basis of the test data is responsible for ensuring the validity of the methodology used and the necessary level of reliability of the diagnosis.

Fourth, the psychologist should be guided by the high efficiency of diagnostics in the development of a comprehensive methodology of psychodiagnostics, carry out scientific research work on improving the method used in the relevant field.

Fifth, in the process of diagnostic work, the psychodiagnostic methodical must comply with the requirements for standardization, process and interpret the received information.

It can be said that the correct use of methodological tools from a psychologist in psychodiagnostic processes carried out with military service personnel, ensuring the confidentiality of psychological informatization, as well as the study of subjects of professional orientation, practical work on production education strengthen the knowledge acquired by military psychologists in the psychodiagnostic Sciences, complement and deepen the ulam. military psychologists are shown on the basis of reliable and vivid examples of how useful the

studied disciplines are in practice, the impact on the development of production areas and, of course, on the effectiveness of the activities of small specialists in the military sphere.